

Research Article**Rising Frequency of Anemia in School Going
Children of Sargodha****¹Hafiza Ayesha Ishaq, ²Hafiz Muhammad Shahzad
and ³Muhammad Tahir**¹DHQ teaching hospital Sargodha, Pakistan²DHQ teaching hospital Sargodha, Pakistan³Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur, Pakistan**ABSTRACT**

ANEMIA: The condition in which RBC mass or Hb concentration is less than 5th percentile for the age. It is a serious concern of the developing countries among school going children and pregnant ladies.

STUDY TYPE: Cross sectional study.

METHOD AND MATERIALS: Department of pediatric medicine in DHQ teaching hospital Sargodha.

RESULTS: The sample size was 150 school going children. Written informed consent was taken from the guardian or parent. Age and sex was noted. The blood sample was taken in EDTA treated tubes and then transported in ice. 11.5mg/dl was taken as cut off value for anemia as WHO guideline.

The data was recorded and then analyzed by SPSS 19. Standard deviation and other qualitative variables were taken like age, gender, anemia was taken. In our study, out of 165 patients, 62 were anemic. Out of 165 cases, 92 were females and 73 were males. 89 were 4-11 years and 71 were between 11-15 years of age. Mean age was calculated as 10.3±3.47.

CONCLUSION: Anemia is highly prevalent in Sargodha among school going children. Proper screening and proper health care must be provided to decrease the frequency.

INTRODUCTION:

Anemia is one of the serious concerns of the developing countries among pregnant females and children. It is a condition characterized by Hb concentration or red cell mass less than 5th percentile for the age. Anemia is one of the major health problems in the world. It is more prevalent in developing countries like Pakistan and still the frequency is on the rise[1]. The prevalence of anemia is 52% in preschool and 46% in school going age children. Malnutrition, poor hygiene, poverty and worm infestation are the main causes. There are three mechanisms by which anemia occurs

1. blood loss

2. decreased production of blood cells.

3. Increased destruction of blood cells.

The etiological factors that result in anemia are malnutrition, iron deficiency, vitamin b12 and folic acid deficiency. Chronic diseases; hiv, tb, aplastic anemia. parasitic infections; hookworm infestation and infections due to schistosomiasis, hemoglobinuria. Pathological diseases. g6pd deficiency[2], thalassemia and sickle cell disease. In our country, malnutrition and malaria are the common causes that cause anemia. Indonesia treated 65% of its anemic cases by iron and folic acid supplementation. The children belonging to the poor socio economic statuses have the high

incidence of anemia due to nutritional deficiencies and non-availability of the health care facilities. Anemia may result in shortness of breath, easy fatigability, dizziness, physical growth retardation tachycardia and cognitive impairment[3].

The exact figures of the frequency of the anemia in school going children is unknown, according to the recent study, the frequency recorded as 41% and another study recorded the findings as 36% in 6-10 years of children and 32% in 10-14 years of children. The variation in the result may be due to difference in the prevalence among different socio economic groups, areas of sampling and local strategies to counter the disease prevalence.

The cross sectional study is done to estimate the frequency of anemia in school going children of Sargodha.

METHODOLOGY: This study was done in the pediatric department of the DHQ teaching hospital Sargodha

STUDY DESIGN: A cross sectional study: study was done from AUGUST 16 to MARCH 17.

SAMPLE SIZE: 165 children were included with confidence level 95% and 7.5% margin of error by non-probability sampling technique.

INCLUSION CRITERIA: School going healthy children with age 4-15 years

Age	Patients	percentage
4-11	89	53.94%
11-15	76	46.06

Table 2

Male	73	44.25%
Female	92	55.75%

Anemia yes 62/165	No 103/165
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Frequency with regards to the gender.

Gender	Yes	No
Male	30	43
Female	32	60

EXCLUSION CRITERIA: Patients with chronic diseases like malnutrition, disorders malabsorption tuberculosis and congenital diseases of heart, aplastic anemia, and those already on treatment for anemia.

DATA COLLECTION:

Pre-designed Performa's were made and informed consent was taken from the guardian or parent of the children fulfilling the inclusion criteria.

Blood samples were taken in EDTA treated tubes and then transported for Hb estimation and CBC.

HB estimation was done by medonic 620.

The findings were recorded on the Performa's as mild(9.5-11.5mg/dl), moderate (7.5-9.50 and severe less than 7.5mg/dl. SPSS 19 was used to analyses the data for quantitative variables like age and hb.

Mean, standard deviation was calculated.

RESULTS:

The data shows 89 children 53.9% were between 4-11 years and 76 children 46.06% were between 11-15 years. Means age 10.5± 3.47 Anemia in school going children was found to be in 62/165 while 103/165 were non anemia.

DISCUSSION:

In our country, anemia is one of the major health problem like other developing and under developed countries. The prevalence has been reported in multiple local and WHO data reports[4]. A child with anemia is seen to have impaired immunity, decreased working capacity, delayed physical growth, tachycardia and cognitive impairment[5]. The study of ours is destined to focus on the prevalence of the disease, so that the statistics may be used to determine the cause and control this treatable disease[5]. In the study, out of 165 children 62 were anemic while 103 cases had no anemia. Out of 62, 32 were male patients and 30 were female patients. The percentage among the age group 11-15 years is higher as compared to lower age group[6].

The findings of our study is in line with the result of other studies. One showing 35% results and another recent study shows 41%. The variability is due to different demographic and socio economic groups. The incidence of anemia and the frequency is much lower than frequencies of the under developed countries like Tanzania and Nigeria i.e 69.5% and 81.5% respectively[7]. This is because Pakistan has much better socio economic status as compared to these countries but it is opposite when compared to developed countries. This treatable disease varies as varies the socio economic statuses of the families. It is more prevalent in families when low or poor socioeconomic back ground as compared to cases from high monthly income as it may be due to low concentration of iron in their food[8].

Another study done locally shows that the prevalence of anemia in 6 months to 2 years of age is much higher as compared to higher age groups, this may be the consequence of inappropriate weaning, no breast feeding and no / limited access to iron containing foods[9].

Another factor that is causing rise in frequency of anemia in children with higher socio economic background is consuming junk food, junk food is healthy and high in calories but is the poor source of iron[10]. The results and findings of our study support that the anemia in the otherwise healthy

school going children is on the rise, conscious and serious measures must be taken to decrease the frequency of anemia by the government by improving the health care provision, iron and folic acid supplements provision and wheat flour fortification besides timely screening and treatment[11].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that the prevalence of anemia is on rise in school going children of Sargodha. Serious measures must be taken to put a check on the rising numbers so that this treatable disease may be controlled.

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